

THE ROLE OF OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *Although people are always faced with opportunities, not everyone has the ability to recognize opportunities and turn them into success. Those who recognize opportunities will have a greater advantage over others in doing business. This article is devoted to the role and importance of entrepreneurial opportunities in entrepreneurial activity.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurial opportunities, opportunity recognition, business, network theory.*

INTRODUCTION

For both new start-up ventures and existing firms, entrepreneurship spurs business expansion, technology advancement, and wealth creation. Entrepreneurial activity is one of the major engines of economic growth and accounts for the majority of new business developments and job creation in many countries. For this reason, the field of entrepreneurship has received a huge amount of attention from policymakers, entrepreneurs and scholars. In academia, entrepreneurship is one of the fastest-growing fields within economics, management, and finance (Klein, 2008). In Shane and Venkataraman's paper (2000), they provide three key reasons why it is worthwhile to study entrepreneurship. First, since large quantities of technical information are embodied in products and services, entrepreneurship is an approach by which technical breakthroughs could be transformed into products and services. Secondly, inefficiency in an economy is identified and improved by entrepreneurship. Thirdly, entrepreneurially driven innovation is significant engine driving social changes.

Opportunity is the key concept within the study of entrepreneurship. Without an opportunity, there would be no entrepreneurship; without an opportunity to target, entrepreneurial activities cannot take place. Focusing on only the characteristics of individual entrepreneurs and neglecting the nature of opportunities they pursue leaves the research into entrepreneurship incomplete. Recognizing this reality, recent researchers have shifted attention away from approaches that focus on identifying those individuals who are more likely to become entrepreneurs towards understanding the nexus of

opportunities and enterprising individuals. (Eckhardt and Shane, 2003; Short et al, 2010).

In an effort to make better sense of the factors shaping entrepreneurial opportunity identification, this research attempts to explore different factors on opportunity identification based on theories that play a role in opportunity identification.

Our goal is to measure the impact of factors on entrepreneurial opportunity recognition. To analyze these perceptual factors, we will use the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) database annual surveys. We will test our hypotheses empirically based on sample data for Russia from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitoring Adult Population Survey. We chose the Global Entrepreneurial Monitor (GEM) for our research because it is one of the standardized data sets on entrepreneurship (Vodă A. I et al., 2020). The GEM survey includes questions about the respondent's attitude to entrepreneurial activity, individual participation in the entrepreneurial process, as well as his motives and aspirations (Bogatyreva et al, 2021). The use of the GEM database allows us to identify and evaluate the various factors that affect entrepreneurial opportunity identification and new venture creation in the entrepreneurial process.

For our study, we suggest estimating logistic regressions where the dependent variable would be the one labelled "opportunity recognition", and the independent variables would be factors that might influence opportunity recognition.

Considering how important entrepreneurship is for economic growth, our findings may have important implications for advising prospective entrepreneurs, and for the direction of entrepreneurship research and development of new theories.

LINKING DIFFERENT THEORIES WITH OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION

Social cognitive theory and opportunity identification

The social cognitive theory emphasized that individuals rely upon their own judgment with regard to their capabilities and the consequent effect of their actions (Camelo-Ordaz et al, 2020). Thus, social cognitive theory suggests that people develop professional aspirations they believe to be feasible and beneficial. As such, the social cognitive theory is based on a cognitive constructivist approach that emphasizes the cognitive feedforward mechanisms where forethought, the anticipation of outcomes, and the active construction of meaning are highlighted. The influence of cognitive characteristics on opportunity identification aimed at specific goals becomes stronger when individuals perceive that contextual factors are beneficial.

Institutional theory and opportunity identification

Institutional theory has been one of the major theoretical frameworks for studying the impact of environmental conditions on opportunity recognition

and evaluation (Edelman & Yli-Renko, 2010). It is argued that entrepreneurs may reduce institutional distances relative to developed markets by engaging in activities such as market research, to assist them in identifying business opportunities. Moreover, it is evident that environmental institutional frameworks influence the opportunity identification processes both positively and negatively (George et al., 2016). Scott (2001) conceptualized pillars of institutions and these pillars that govern organizations are: first, the regulatory dimension which includes existing national laws and rules that will sanction certain behavior while restricting other types of behavior; second, the normative component is considered more informal and is made up of social norms and values that are shared socially.

These institutional profiles or dimensions have been widely accepted to influence the rate of formation and growth of small businesses across nations. However, researchers emphasize that when these institutional dimensions are generalised across environments, they generalize relevance. So although the institutional dimensions are connected in some aspects, they should be treated as conceptually distinct, requiring that each dimension be assessed separately because each institution affects specific domains in a different manner (Stenholm et al., 2013). Furthermore, given the possibility that entrepreneurs think differently due to the unusual contexts (Short et al., 2010), understanding the influence that the institutional environment may have on opportunity identification is important.

Network theory and opportunity identification

Following Social network theory, individual's social ties can stimulate the ability to recognize entrepreneurial opportunities and entrepreneurial pursuits (Ozgen & Minsky, 2007). This view is supported by Birley and Westhead (1994) arguing that social ties of a person can provide the required resources and information about the suitability of recognized opportunities such as the sources of business opportunities, the information about the feasibility of different opportunities. Ardichvili et al (2000) proclaimed "that entrepreneurs who have extended networks identify significantly more opportunities" than those who recognized opportunities individually. This is unquestionable, since social network creates a wide range of individuals' database, leading them to gather and evaluate a pool of new ideas.

Factors

The concept of entrepreneurial opportunity identification is central to entrepreneurship research (Bogatyreva, K., 2021). Entrepreneurial opportunity underlies the entrepreneurial process and includes the early stages of new economic activity and organizational development (McMullen et al., 2007, Chen, P. C., 2020). Hence, a positive assessment of entrepreneurial opportunities that can be identified by an individual can be a direct first part of new venture creation. But, why do some people recognize vital entrepreneurial opportunities while others recognize nothing?

Entrepreneurial opportunities are everywhere, but many cannot identify them. However, some individuals see things that others do not. To answer the question of why and how some people can identify opportunities, while others are not, we will be able to identify by answering the following question:

What factors impact entrepreneurial opportunity identification in the entrepreneurial process?

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES BASED ON THEORIES

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy refers to a person's belief that he or she can successfully perform the various roles and tasks essential to entrepreneurship. It has been argued that entrepreneurial self-efficacy is positively related to opportunity identification (Ozgen and Baron, 2007). For example, Gibbs (2009) argue that the belief that one possesses certain skills makes the difference between those individuals who are more likely to recognize opportunities and those who do not. Boudreaux et al. (2019) and Godwin et al. (2016) argue that an entrepreneur's skills alone are insufficient for opportunity recognition. They also need to trust in their own abilities to achieve their desired goals, which in turn lead to a greater probability of perceiving opportunities (Boudreaux et al., 2019; Godwin et al., 2016). When people believe they have the experience, knowledge and skills necessary to start their own venture, their attitude becomes more positive and proactive towards the search for opportunities (Ardichvili et al., 2003; Drnovšek et al., 2010). Moreover, Baron (2006) notes that those with high levels of self-efficacy tend to have wider social networks and are consequently, able to access more information that aids them in recognizing opportunities (Ozgen and Baron, 2007).

Fear of Failure

Another important feature when analyzing entrepreneurial opportunities is the fear of failure. Fear of failure measures the negative emotions that result from perceiving various threats, and it is a limiting factor in identifying business opportunities and creating ventures (Nefzi, N., 2018). At the same time, the perception of potential barriers and obstacles is a direct driver of the fear of activating failure, which immediately negatively affects the assessment and use of entrepreneurial opportunities (Kollmann et al., 2017). Hence, the fear of failure can be seen as a cognitive condition that prevents the emergence of new business.

Prior experience

The previous work experience is an important criterion for identifying business opportunities because they provide entrepreneurs with information about the market in which they operate (Shane, S., 2000). Experience-based knowledge can guide assumptions and interpretations of market stimuli, which can help generate ideas. It is argued that entrepreneurs can identify

opportunities that others cannot do because of the specialized knowledge they have gained through their entrepreneurial experiences (Miralles, F.,2016).

Social network

Social network connects individuals with entrepreneurs that help identify opportunities, collect and distribute scarce resources, thereby making it a more financially viable business activity. Social networking increases individuals' trust by reducing uncertainty, supporting and sharing experiences (Minniti, 2005). Hence, it can become an important factor in entrepreneurial opportunities by encouraging socialization towards entrepreneurship (Chen & He., 2011). In addition, people who know the entrepreneur well are more likely to identify entrepreneurial opportunities faster and engage in entrepreneurial activity.

CONCLUSION

There are theoretical and practical outcomes of this research. Theoretically, the results of this research can be seen as support for an existing theory by better explaining the results of previous research in the field of identifying entrepreneurial opportunities (D'souza, R. R. 2009). From a practical point of view, the results of this study provide people with theoretical knowledge in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as procedural training for individuals on how to identify entrepreneurial opportunities. In general, the study of these factors influencing the identification of opportunities will be one of the important literature for individuals to engage in successful entrepreneurship in the future, as well as to address the problems associated with identifying business opportunities in the entrepreneurial process.

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